

Coercivity Dependence on PrFeB thin films with Strong Perpendicular Magnetic Anisotropy

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Rare-earth transition metal thin films hold great potential for implementation in devices at the micro and nanoscale [1-3]. While Nd₂Fe₁₄B and Pr₂Fe₁₄B share almost the same intrinsic magnetic properties (M_s , K_u , T_c ...), Nd₂Fe₁₄B has a limited use for low temperature applications (i.e. aerospace) due to the spin reorientation that occurs at 135 K [4]. This limitation can be overcome using Pr₂Fe₁₄B, whose magnetization direction remains along the c-axis until 4.2 K [4]. The understanding and optimization of these systems is of great importance when attempting their integration in novel miniaturized devices [5].

In this study, high coercivity PrFeB thin films of 100 nm have been fabricated by magnetron sputtering. The effect on the substrate temperature (T_s) in the structure and morphology and its resulting impact on the magnetic properties has been evaluated.

A highly textured growth of Pr₂Fe₁₄B is achieved when $T_s \leq 600^\circ\text{C}$ according to the X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis (Fig. 1a). Pr₂Fe₁₄B crystalline phase is accompanied by a Pr-rich phase that can be identified in all the XRD patterns. The correlation between the size and distribution of these Pr-rich areas with T_s and the role they play in the magnetism of the samples has also been thoroughly studied by Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDX) (Fig. 1c). Regardless of T_s , all films present strong perpendicular magnetic anisotropy which is in good accordance with the c-axis oriented preferential growth (Fig. 1d). Out of plane coercivities up to 15 kOe have been obtained at RT for $T_s = 600^\circ\text{C}$. Furthermore, Magnetic Force Microscopy measurements (MFM) prove the existence of interacting magnetic domains in all cases. The suitability of these Pr₂Fe₁₄B thin films for low temperature

Figure 1. a) XRD pattern of PrFeB thin films grown at different T_s . b) Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of a PrFeB film grown at 600°C . c) EDX mapping of a PrFeB film with a $T_s = 600^\circ\text{C}$ showing the distribution of Pr and Fe (c.1) Pr distribution (c.2) Fe distribution (c.3). The scale bar is 800 nm in all cases. d) Room temperature hysteresis loop for $T_s = 600^\circ\text{C}$

applications has also been investigated.

Notes and References

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